

CIVIL LEGAL RELATIONS REGARDING SETTLEMENT LANDS ARE BEING IMPROVED (USING THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN AS AN EXAMPLE)

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Abstract. This article describes and substantiates, based on scientific analysis, issues such as the digitalization of civil law relations related to settlement lands and the application of artificial intelligence as one of the urgent tasks in our country. It also covers the large-scale reforms carried out in recent years regarding legal guarantees, particularly the improvement of legal relations and legislative mechanisms related to land in the development of constitutional and legal reforms.

Key words: settlement lands, composition of settlement lands, civil law relations on settlement lands, property rights on settlement lands, benefits on settlement lands in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, proposals and recommendations on civil law guarantees of settlement lands in the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Introduction

In our country, addressing legal relations regarding settlement lands, analyzing them, and increasing their effectiveness are considered among the important priority tasks. In this process, practices have been established to ensure accuracy and transparency in land use, radically eliminate corruption risks, simplify the system of online and offline registration of land ownership rights, and optimize land tax. We consider it necessary to note that while such reforms are being carried out in relation to eight categories of land legislation in the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is important to specifically express opinions about the significance and necessity of scientific research on settlement lands among these categories.

The Republic of Karakalpakstan is located in the northwestern part of Uzbekistan, in the lower reaches of the Amu Darya River, on the southern shore of the Aral Sea. The total land area of Karakalpakstan is 166.6 thousand square kilometers, ranking it first among the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in terms of size. The population of the republic exceeds 2,035,100 people. The administrative-territorial structure of the republic consists of 16 districts and 1 city: Amudarya, Beruniy, Bozatau, Ellikkala, Turtkul, Kegeyli, Chimbay, Karauzyak, Takhtakupyr, Kanlykul, Shumanay, Kungrad, Muynak, Khojeyli, Takhiatash, Nukus districts and the capital city of Nukus. The Republic of Karakalpakstan is considered a sovereign republic with a parliamentary form of government within the Republic of Uzbekistan. Karakalpakstan has its own Constitution, flag, emblem, and anthem. The Constitution and laws of Karakalpakstan have been developed in accordance with the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and legal mechanisms have been created on this basis[1].

Literature analysis and methods

According to Article 47[2] of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "Everyone has the right to housing.

No one may be deprived of housing without a court decision and in a manner contrary to the law. An owner deprived of housing is guaranteed prior and equivalent compensation for the cost of the housing and any losses incurred, in cases and manner prescribed by law.

The State encourages housing construction and creates conditions for the realization of the right to housing.

The procedure for providing housing to socially vulnerable categories of the population is determined by law." These constitutional and legal norms apply throughout the administrative territory of our country and also affect the legal relations of the population living in the Republic of Karakalpakstan regarding their privately owned housing.

Article 51 of the Constitution of the Republic of Karakalpakstan[3] states: "The foundation of Karakalpakstan's economy, aimed at developing market relations, is property in its various forms. The State, taking into account the priority of consumer rights, guarantees freedom of economic activity, entrepreneurship and labor, equal rights and equal legal protection for all forms of ownership.

Private property, like other forms of ownership, is inviolable and protected by the state. The fact that "the owner can be deprived of his property only in cases and in the manner prescribed by law" is defined as a constitutional and legal norm, constantly reminds us that the property rights of the population living in this territory should be exercised on the basis of the law and demands it from each owner.

The composition of lands of settlements is determined in accordance with

As stipulated in Article 59[4], all lands within the administrative boundaries of cities and towns belong to the lands of cities and towns. These lands include: lands of urban and settlement development; lands of general use; lands used in agriculture and other lands; lands occupied by forest plantations; lands intended for industrial, transport, communications, defense and other purposes; lands of protected natural areas; lands of the water fund; reserve lands. The legislation of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Karakalpakstan fully supports the effective use of all categories of the land fund, and representatives of both nations consider it important to use these legal opportunities as a requirement of the times.

Today, large-scale construction and landscaping work is being carried out in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Life in Karakalpakstan is completely changing, all cities and districts, villages, and mahallas are acquiring a new look, and modern enterprises, educational, medical, cultural, sports, and other social facilities, as well as communication networks, are being built. This testifies to the fact that the role of the Republic of Karakalpakstan in the socio-economic life of our country, as in all spheres, as a civil-legal relationship with the lands of settlements, is increasing.

It should be noted that in order to clearly and transparently implement the legal norms of land legislation in practice, digitalization and the use of artificial intelligence in this huge sphere have been formed in a completely new way, the automated information system "Privatization of Land,"

Electronic systems such as the "E-auksion" electronic trading platform, the "E-qaror" system, the "Kadastr.uz," "Gis.kadastr.uz," "Yer.geoportal.uz," "Davreestr.uz" systems, the "Uzcad" program, and the "Recognition of Rights" system have been created, and these systems are also being effectively implemented in the administrative territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. In this regard, for the generous and hardworking people of the Republic of

Karakalpakstan, the great attention paid by our esteemed President Shavkat Mirziyoyev and the processes of carrying out strategic practical work are of great importance.

In particular, during the President's visit to the Republic of Karakalpakstan on February 23-24, 2022, large-scale work was carried out. In accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 30, 2022 No. PP-264 "On Additional Measures for the Development of Entrepreneurship in the Northern Districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan"[5], indicators for the re-commissioning of irrigated land plots withdrawn from agricultural use in the northern districts for 2022-2024 were approved, and within the framework of this program

On an area of 421 hectares, shrubs were cleared, and the land was leveled. New orchards have been established on 116 hectares of the developed land. Also, local initiators have developed targeted lists for the development of 12.8 thousand hectares of land. At the expense of other sown areas, 8,000 hectares were allocated to the needy population listed in the "Iron Notebook," "Youth Notebook," and "Women's Notebook" based on a transparent mechanism for farming. In addition, 15.2 billion soums have been allocated from the Fund of the Council of Farmers, Dehkan Farms and Owners of Household Plots of Uzbekistan for the implementation of projects in the regions of Amudarya, Turtkul, Beruniy

and Ellikkala districts, a list of citizens was compiled for the creation of compact greenhouses in 4 thousand households [6]. It should be noted that the fulfillment of these practical tasks served as the basis for the emergence of legal relations of various degrees regarding the land fund, in particular, the lands of settlements, and their formation throughout the territory.

According to Academician Kh. Rakhmonkulov, the characteristic features of real estate are that they cannot be separated from land, therefore they are characterized as objects of high value [7].

Civilist scholar Professor N.F. Imomov and Doctor of Philosophy in Law U. Khadjiev emphasized that relations with land as an object of civil rights should be directed towards an individualized land plot, promoting the implementation of relations arising from the right holder in the upper layer of the land [8].

As a logical continuation of the ideas, taking into account that the full legal regulation of legal relations related to the lands of settlements in the territory of our republic, and thus in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, is not a current problem, but one of the problems that has been passing from year to year for many years, in particular, the practice of providing a number of benefits and privileges for the population of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and their legitimate interests has been formed, and in practice, we will analyze on the example of some legislative acts that their application in legal relations is of great importance.

Resolution ~~~ of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan

on the basis of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 3, 2016 No. 251 "On a comprehensive inventory of real estate objects owned by individuals and legal entities for the period 2016-2017" [9] without title documents

Presidential Decree No. UP-5421 of April 20, 2018, "On Additional Measures for Social Support of Citizens and Conducting a One-Time Nationwide Campaign to Recognize Ownership Rights to Unauthorized Residential Premises" [10] and

50,361 without title documents in accordance with Resolution No. 461 [11]

housing rights were recognized. However, despite the fact that conditions for the Karakalpak people, like in other regions, are changing for the better, in some legal relations there are gaps in the mechanisms of legislation on private property, that is, according to the data of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, there are an additional 43,432 houses, the ownership rights of which are not recognized, and in order to ensure the property rights of this segment of the population, it is no exaggeration to say that this led to the issuance of a separate normative legal act in the region.

The state has once again demonstrated its enormous potential in creating appropriate conditions for the protection of the rights, freedoms, and legally protected interests of citizens. Decree ~~~ of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 28, 2023

Decree No. UP-119 "On Social Support of the Population of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and Recognition of Rights to Housing Built by Individuals" [12]. This normative legal act was met with positive applause by the Karakalpak people and the owners, who are the subjects of law, and the right of citizens to lease a land plot on the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, where residential houses built without legal documents are located, as well as the property rights of private owners to buildings and structures located on it, were recognized on a preferential basis.

Although our people living in other regions of Uzbekistan, namely the regions and the city of Tashkent, envied the benefits and opportunities provided to the Karakalpak people in this regard, however, this process was not left to chance and continued as a practical priority.

According to the Department of the Chamber of State Cadastres of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, practical work has also been carried out to create the experience of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, and we can see in specific statistical figures that progressive results have been achieved. In 2022, a total of 39,747 applications were submitted by individuals and legal entities for state registration of real estate objects, of which 733 were by public service centers, 2,884 were canceled for valid reasons, 1,586 are being studied in the process, 34,544 objects of real estate were fully legally justified, and 1,605 were registered as mortgage and lease agreements [13].

On the basis of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 8, 2023 No. UP-129 "On Additional Measures to Create Favorable Conditions for Entrepreneurs in the Republic of Karakalpakstan" [14] a number of benefits were provided. Including

Firstly, the procedure for privatizing land plots, buildings, and structures for entrepreneurs who have fulfilled investment obligations in small and youth industrial and entrepreneurial zones has been established;

Secondly, in the event of non-sale within 3 months of state property objects on public auctions in the region, a procedure has been introduced for their transfer on the basis of an electronic competition with the obligation to invest in the applicant who submitted the best proposal;

Thirdly, in 2023-2024, a system has been introduced for the provision of land plots to project initiators, including enterprises with foreign investments, on the right of direct long-term lease based on the decision of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, with the obligation to invest 1 million US dollars in the city of Nukus and 300 thousand US dollars in the remaining districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan;

Fourthly, in 2023-2024, the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, based on its decision, has been authorized, as an exception, to change the category of the land fund of

non-irrigated land plots (pastures, lands inaccessible to water, low-fertility) within the forest fund and agricultural land.

We clearly see in practice that the content of the listed regulatory legal acts and the opportunities provided through them for the Karakalpak population and their legitimate interests are not the end, and we must constantly interpret and promote them positively, and understand that it is our civic duty and obligation for every person.

By the esteemed President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev in 2024

On January 10 [15], he held a meeting to analyze the work on the socio-economic development of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and discuss future tasks. It states: "In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, 12 out of 15 districts were previously subsidized, and today Karakalpakstan has become a region with its own income. In particular, more than 5.3 thousand projects worth 15 trillion soums have been implemented. One million 800 thousand hectares of green forests have been created on the dried-up territory of the Aral Sea. Housing conditions of 51 thousand families were improved, and construction and repair work was carried out in 401 mahallas. The standard of living of the population has increased. It was also noted that as a result of attracting a foreign grant to increase soil fertility in agriculture, water-saving technologies will be introduced on 6 thousand hectares of land, and laser leveling of 31 thousand hectares is planned. Consequently, the solution of these issues is also the result of the establishment of legal relations concerning the interests of the people of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, private property, as well as the enormous work done for the future.

RESULTS

Thus, it should be noted that the effectiveness of large-scale legal reforms regarding the lands of settlements in the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan can be listed as follows:

Firstly, the stability and protection of property rights were guaranteed. It is no coincidence that the main goal is to ensure stability in civil legal relations and reduce legal disputes.

Secondly, the processes of economic development and urbanization have increased, i.e., land privatization has supported economic transformations, made a significant contribution to the creation of new jobs, financial inclusion, and sustainable urbanization. This made it possible to effectively use land for entrepreneurship and housing construction in civil law relations.

Thirdly, legal relations regarding the land of settlements have been simplified. Civil transactions, such as the purchase, lease, pledge, or contribution of land plots to the authorized capital of legal entities, were legally supported. This allowed real estate owners to carry out financial operations and effectively manage the land.

Fourthly, the principles of transparency and fairness in the legal relations of settlements with respect to land have been raised to the level of the main requirement. It has been strictly established that privatization will be carried out only through the "E-auksion" electronic trading platform, which ensured that prices are based on market value and reduced the risk of various forms of corruption. As a result, the principles of legality, voluntariness, and openness increased trust in relations between owners and employees of authorized state bodies in civil law relations.

Fifthly, it unconditionally guaranteed the protection of settlements from the compulsory seizure of their lands from owners. Land plots can be acquired only by a court decision, for state needs, or seized in emergency situations; in this case, the state has assumed the responsibility

for payment and compensation. This ensured the fairness of legal relations, protecting the legitimate interests of each citizen or owner.

Sixthly, the "Uzcad" program and the "Recognition of Rights" system were created as state control and important legal guarantees in the formation of legal relations regarding the land of settlements, and in

Although Article 188 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan states: "The right of ownership of citizens and legal entities to land plots arises in cases, in the manner, and under the conditions stipulated by law" [16], we can see that issues of civil law relations, the object of transactions and contracts, certain categories of the land fund, and property rights are regulated. In this regard, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Based on the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 7, 2020 No. UP-6061 "On Measures for the Fundamental Improvement of the System of Land Records and State Cadastres"[17] and the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 20, 2022 No. PP-405 "On Measures for Further Improvement of the Activities of the Cadastral Agency under the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan"[18], taking into account that from October 1, 2020, decisions, protocols of auctions and tenders, notarized transactions, and other documents providing for the emergence, change, transfer, restriction, and termination of rights to land plots will enter into force after state registration in the "Uzkad" Integrated Information System for Cadastral and Real Estate Registration, the results of the inventory conducted in each of our regions will be reflected in the electronic database.

As a specific example, in accordance with

Based on the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Recognition of Rights to Unauthorized Occupied Land Plots and Buildings and Structures Constructed on Them" No. ZRU-937 of August 5 [19], we can cite the inventories conducted in each of our regions. As a result of statistical data, we consider it very important to dwell on the work carried out in the Republic of Karakalpakstan as of August 1, 2025.

Thus, the total land area of the Republic of Karakalpakstan is 16,656,123 hectares, of which 32,984 hectares are lands of settlements, and this territory constitutes 0.2% of the total land area of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. The total number of real estate objects is 482,664, of which the number of individual residential buildings is 385,024, the number of apartments in multi-story buildings is 49,526, the number of non-residential premises is 48,114. An electronic map of 98% of all land use category indicators was created in the UZCAD program. The level of state registration was 98% [20].

In the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, as in every region of our republic, the land area of settlements increased year by year in proportion to the population, and the indicated indicators appeared. This led to the rapid development of civil law relations arising between subjects of law and owners, and the Republic of Karakalpakstan gained experience in their legal regulation.

In conclusion, we believe that in the draft Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is planned to be adopted in the new edition, it is necessary to reflect specific civil law legal norms regarding land fund categories, as well as legal terms related to the lands of settlements.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Based on the foregoing, the following proposals and recommendations regarding the application of civil law relations concerning the lands of settlements in the Republic of Karakalpakstan can be listed. Including

Firstly, although the practice of using the capabilities of artificial intelligence is used in all spheres and in the activities of state bodies in our country, it is advisable to include legal norms on digitalization in the content of the Land Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan regarding the use of artificial intelligence in our national legislation, for example, in legal relations regarding the lands of settlements;

Secondly, in our country, the use of artificial intelligence is carried out in the process of legal relations and the use of the objects included in them, however, in relation to the use of artificial intelligence in legal relations concerning the lands of settlements, the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Ex. 81-101), there is a high need to introduce legal norms on digitalization;

Thirdly, the fact that reforms related to the lands of settlements and lands included in them were carried out by authorized state bodies as administrative and legal relations with an indicator of 98% is a very significant result, however, we believe that civil law relations related to the lands of settlements in the Republic of Karakalpakstan provide an advanced experience of reliable and transparent use by our people, in particular, the Karakalpak people, legal entities, and each owner of perfect systems that effectively use information and communication technologies in our country.

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